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Prevalence and incidence of multiple sclerosis in Las Palmas, Canary Islands, Spain

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Abstract

Objectives: To determine the prevalence and incidence of multiple sclerosis (MS) in the city of Las Palmas (Canary Islands, Spain), geographically belonging to north-western Africa, but with European ancestry.

Methods: This population-based survey was conducted for a period of 5 years (1998-2002) in a Sanitary District of Las Palmas city (28 degrees 20' N), with a population of 82,623 inhabitants. Multiple sources were periodically investigated for case ascertainment. Patients with definite and probable MS were included.

Results: Sixty-four patients with MS were identified on prevalence day, December 31, 2002. According to Poser's criteria the crude prevalence rate was 77.5 per 100,000 (95% CI: 59.7-98.9). This rate decreased to 73.8 (95% CI: 56.5-94.8) according to McDonald's criteria. Age-adjusted rates for the world and European standard populations were 61.6 (95% CI: 47.1-78.9) and 70.6 (95% CI: 55-89), respectively. Prevalence was higher for women aged 25-44 years. In 17 patients onset of MS occurred within the study period. Average annual incidence was 4.1 per 100,000 (95% CI: 2.4-6.6).

Conclusions: The prevalence and incidence rates in Las Palmas city are close to those reported from Continental Spain and other countries of southern Europe with similar social and ethnic background. These results highlight the role of racial-ethnic factors in the genesis of MS.